

Germplasm improvement

Genetic resources

Mobile genetic elements useful for classifying and determining relationships between rice strains

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Morphological and physiological studies have played an important role in classifying species in the genus *Oryza*. Although detailed information on the classification of rice species has been accumulated with the development of molecular biological technology, relationships between *Oryza* species with AA genome have not been clarified.

We have identified 37 members of p-SINE1, a plant SINE (short interspersed elements) first found in rice (see figure), located at various loci. Most of these members are at the corresponding loci in *Oryza* species with the AA genome. However, several of them are present in a few *Oryza* species. Besides those described previously, a member of p-SINE1-r30 is only in *O. sativa*, p-SINE1-r29 is in all the AA genome *Oryza* species except for *O. longistaminata*, and p-SINE1-r25 is in all of the AA genome *Oryza* species except for *O. meridionalis* (see table).

Another member, p-SINE1-r38, contained an insertion that was 1536 bp long, with imperfect terminal inverted repeats of about 13 bp beginning with 5'-CACTA—3' (see figure). The insertion is

Distribution of p-SINE1^a

Species	p-SINE1-r30	p-SINE1-r29	p-SINE1-r25	p-SINE1-r38
<i>O. sativa</i> cv Nipponbare	+	+ ^b	±	+ ^c
cv IR36	+	+	±	+ ^c
<i>O. glaberrima</i> W025	—	+	+	+ ^c
<i>O. longistaminata</i> W1451 P1	—	—	+	—
<i>O. meridionalis</i> W1625	—	+	—	+
<i>O. glumaepatula</i> W1192	—	+	±	+ ^c

^ap-SINE1 members identified in *O. sativa*. The presence or absence of each p-SINE1 member at the respective locus was examined by PCR using a relevant pair of primers that hybridize to the regions flanking the p-SINE1 member. + and — indicate that the fragments with or without p-SINE1, respectively, are generated by PCR. ^bPCR fragments with p-SINE1 have a tandem duplication. ^cPCR fragments with p-SINE1 contain *Tnr3*. ± indicates that both fragments with and without p-SINE1 are generated by PCR.

Structures of p-SINE1 (a) and p-SINE1-r38 (b).

similar to that of the members of the En/Spm transposable element family such as En/Spm in maize, Tam1 in snapdragon, Tgm1 in soybean, Pis1 in pea, and Tpn1 in Japanese morning glory. This insertion sequence is thus named *Tnr3* (transposable element in rice #3). The *Tnr3* also carries long subterminal regions containing direct and inverted repeats of short DNA sequences of 15 bp, another characteristic of

the En/Spm family. *O. sativa*, *O. rufipogon*, *O. glaberrima*, and *O. glumaepatula* contain p-SINE1-r38 with *Tnr3*, but *O. meridionalis* contains only p-SINE1-r38 (see table). *O. longistaminata*, however, does not contain p-SINE1-r38.

The p-SINE1 members listed in the table might become useful DNA markers for classifying and determining relationships among *Oryza* species with AA genome. ■

Cytological analysis of a natural hybrid between *Oryza minuta* and *O. officinalis*

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Intergenic or interspecific hybrids are important for studying the evolutionary relationships between plant species, particularly those occurring spontaneously in nature. One *Oryza* population collected in 1990 from San Roque, Hilongos, Leyte, Philippines (P90-18; by D. A. Vaughan, L. Engle, N. Altoveros, E. Quintana, and T. Borromeo) was completely sterile, with nondehiscent anthers, nonstainable pollen grains, and no seed set. Morphologically,

this population resembled *O. minuta* J. S. Presl. ex C. B. Presl., a tetraploid *Oryza* species endemic to the Philippines that has 48 chromosomes containing two distantly related genomes (BBCC). This population was originally identified as "sterile *O. minuta*" and maintained in a nursery greenhouse for further observation.

Cytological observation of both root tip cells and pollen mother cells (PMCs) confirmed this population is a triploid

Meiotic configurations in metaphase I of the "sterile *O. minuta*."

Cells observed (no.)	2n=	a ^a r ^a	Chromosome configuration					Chiasma/cell
			I	II ₁ ^b	II ₂ ^b	III	IV	
15	36		8.60 (5-14)	1.74 (1-4)	10.13 (6-14)	0.93 (0-2)	0.20 (0-1)	24.80 (19-30)

^aa = average, r = range; ^bII₁ = rod bivalents, II₂ = ring bivalents.

Anaphase I of the "sterile *O. minuta*" showing 36 chromosomes, including 11 laggards; two overlapping chromosomes are indicated by the arrow head.

(2n=3x) with 36 chromosomes. Meiotic analysis of its PMCs further indicated its irregular meiosis at different stages. An average of 8.60 univalents, 11.87 bivalents, and a certain amount of multivalents were scored at metaphase I (see table). Meiosis beyond metaphase I was complicated by

other irregularities. Numerous chromosomes were observed to lag at anaphase I and anaphase II (see figure). One chromatid bridge accompanied by a fragment was found at anaphase I. Micro-nuclei were scored in all quarters. We concluded that this "sterile *O. minuta*" was

a spontaneous hybrid between *O. minuta* and *O. officinalis*, which is classified as a diploid wild rice species (2n=2x=24) containing the CC genome. The sterile population was reported to grow sympatrically with *O. minuta* and *O. officinalis* at the original site.

Numerical analysis of the meiotic configurations in this natural hybrid suggested the best fitting genomic model to be 2:1, with a χ^2 value (relative affinity of the most closely related genomes) of 0.969 and WSSD (weighted sums of squares of differences) of 17.1. This indicates the presence of two closely related genomes (homologous) and one distantly related genome (homoeologous) in the natural hybrid. The two closely related genomes should therefore be the CC genomes derived, respectively, from *O. minuta* (BBCC) and *O. officinalis* (CC). The high frequency of bivalent formation reveals high homology between the CC genomes from the two species. The single distantly related genome should then be the B genome derived from *O. minuta*. The relatively high frequency of multivalents (>1 per cell) and low univalents indicates homoeologous pairing between either the CC genome or the B genome. Furthermore, reciprocal chromosomal translocations in the CC genome of one of the parental species probably causes multivalents to be formed. The chromatid bridge suggests an inversion of a chromosome segment in one of the genomes. ■

Screening RFLP probes for differentiating indicas and japonicas

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Restriction fragment length polymorphism (RFLP) is an effective and reliable tool for classifying the subspecies of *Oryza sativa* L. However, a RFLP survey of the entire rice genome is time-consuming, labor-intensive, and expensive. We report our progress on identifying a set of RFLP probes for differentiating indicas and japonicas.

In our previous RFLP survey of three indica testers and three japonica testers used for screening widely compatible varieties in China, 68 out of 160 probes produced identical hybridization patterns among rice varieties of the same subspecies and different patterns among rice varieties of different subspecies (Zheng et al 1994). Seven established varieties of various origins for both indicas and japonicas were used in RFLP analysis with 68 probes, combined with restriction enzymes *Dra*I, *Eco*RI, *Eco*RV, and *Hind*III. Twenty-one probes regenerated different hybridization patterns between indica and japonica subspecies with at least one enzyme. The majority also regenerated identical patterns within a subspecies. A set of 13 probes for

differentiating subspecies was selected based on Southern blotting performance and chromosome distribution (Qian et al 1995).

To determine the applicability of the indica-japonica differentiation probes, 52 cultivated Asian rice varieties with different geographic distributions were selected and assayed with 100 DNA probes in combination with a single enzyme. The proportions of shared DNA fragments and genetic distances between varieties were quantified according to Nei (1987) based on 184 polymorphic fragments of 65 polymorphic probes. Using the unweighted paired group method with arithmetic mean (Sokal and Michener 1958), the varieties were clearly clustered into two groups.